

ORFIRA Report on Progress and activity to date

“ Introducing an OR Framework & Integrating OR indicators into Research Assessment”

1. Initial steps

After notification of being awarded CoARA Boost funding for the ORFIRA project between University College Cork and Amsterdam Universities Medical Centre, the project team took two initial steps to kick-off the project:

- Developing a practical project outline between the partner institutions UCC and AUMC by transferring the proposal timelines into the reality of two busy academic calendars of the partner institutions.
- Establishing links between the ORFIRA project and the work of both the recently established Open Research coordination group and the existing Research Integrity Champion group in UCC in order to embed the project within the context of both groups’ activities (both groups complement each other’s efforts with many representatives active in both initiatives). A summary of presentations to both groups can be found in annex 1.

2. Scoping Visit

A scoping visit from AUMC’s project coordinator to Cork was deemed more efficient than a UCC visit to AUMC (as originally planned as per project proposal). This visit was arranged for Nov 27 & 28 2025 with an agenda of meetings with as many representatives of the above mentioned groups, the VP for Research of Innovation UCC, and members of CATALISI project to explore leveraging the project learnings as per agenda below:

Rita Santos Visit to UCC – Nov 27/28		
Thursday, Nov 27th:		Room / Venue:
From 9.00:	Arrival at UCC & introductions	OVPRI PA Room
	Meeting with Open Research Coordination Group and Research Integrity Champion Group Opened by Prof John Cryan	
10.30 – 12.30:	3x 20 min Presentations by Rita + Q&A	Library Conference Room
13.00 – 14.00:	Lunch with John Cryan, David O’Connell, Simone O’Rourke	Lea’s (Glucksman)
14.30 – 15.30:	Meeting with Irene Kavanagh & Aoife Coffey (Research Roots)	OVPRI PA Room
16.00 – 16.30:	Meeting with David O’Connell, Siobhan Cusack, Simone (Research Strategy)	David’s Office
19.00	Dinner with David O’Connell and Simone O’Rourke	River Club - River Lee Hotel
Friday, Nov 28th:		
10.00 – 11.00:	Meeting with Richard Scriven & David O’Connell / Open Research Policy	OVPRI PA Room
11.00 – 12.00:	Meeting with Simone O’Rourke & David O’Connell: Next Steps	David’s Office

The central session of the visit saw in-depth presentations on AUMC and VU Recognition & Rewards Programme, RIOS (Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science), VU’s

Open Science Program (e.g. policies, awareness campaigns, training resources) as per annex 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

The visit was successful crystallizing the additional expertise sought from UCC:

- Open Access: (nearly 100% Open Access at VU)
- FAIR data management:
 - infrastructure for research data management
 - data steward coordination
- Gamification of engagement with Open Research/Open Science games
- CoARA – progress on AUMC's institutional CoARA action plan
- Citizen Science Hub
 - processes and engagement with the public
 - coordination of multiple Citizen Science initiatives
 - resources
- practical implementation Recognition and Rewards programme:
 - integration of indicators into annual reviews, promotions

These requests will be addressed during the upcoming visit to Amsterdam in March 2026.

3. Challenges / Hurdles experienced to date

Competing priorities continue to be a hurdle, e.g. in the demand for key staff members' time in order to advance the project in a meaningful way. Faculty representatives are supportive of the agenda in principle, but action and support are slowed down significantly by competing priorities.

4. Impact to date

Growing awareness of both Open Research practices and CoARA principles in UCC due to:

- Open Research Coordination formalized and approved by academic approval board with various supporting documents in progress/approved: Terms of Reference, Open Research Statement, Open Research policy
- Re-invigoration of research integrity champion group (advanced in tandem with the Open Research coordination group / benefit due to the interlinked nature of both group agendas)
- Presentations given by AUMC to UCC highlighted the advanced stage of the agenda in other EU countries and the need for more urgency.

5. Next Steps

5.1 Knowledge Transfer Visit to Amsterdam (VU / AUMC)

The immediate next step is a knowledge exchange visit of a UCC delegation to AUMC which has been the focus up to now.

5.1.1 UCC delegation to AUMC

There will be a UCC delegation of 8 staff with representation from

Department	Focus area:
OVPRI UCC	Open research coordination, CoARA
OVPRI	Open research coordination, CoARA
UCC Library	Open Access, Fair Data steward, Open research coordination
UCC Library	FAIR data, data stewardship
OVPRI	Research Culture, Research Integrity
OVPRI	Open research coordination
ECR (UCC),	Open research for Early Career Researchers
PhD candidate (UCC)	Open research for Early Career Researchers

5.1.2 Visit Agenda

The visit agenda is outlined in annex 6 will cover the areas with knowledge exchange opportunities with relevant experts of VU and AUMC:

- VU CoARA action
- embedding OR in research assessment policies
- Recognition & Rewards policies
- Data stewardship network, Open Access
- Research Integrity policies & procedures
- VU Open Science Program & training,
- Citizen Science initiatives
- Open Science indicators and criteria into R&R policies.

The outcome of this visit will define the implementation of tangible Open Research and responsible research assessment practices for the remainder of the project. All this will enable the finalisation of a CoARA action plan and the implementation of the priority actions.

Annex 1 – Project Updates to Open Research Coordination group and Research Integrity
Champion group at UCC

ORFIRA Update Oct 15: Scoping Visit Nov 27/28, 2025

“ORFIRA” - *Introducing an OR Framework & Integrating OR indicators into Research Assessment*

Funding: €40K CoARA Boost Funding (2nd Call) – *Teaming Project (Knowledge Transfer)*

Duration: Sept 2025 – August 2026

Partner Institution: **Amsterdam UMC**
Universitair Medische Centra

Scoping Visit from: **Dr Rita Figueiras Alves dos Santos,**
Coordinator of the Netherlands Research Integrity Network (NRIN)
Project Leader of Amsterdam's Centre for Research Integrity & Open Science (RIOS)

Purpose: **How to leverage Amsterdam’s Open Science experience and expertise:**

- Policy & Implementation
- Open Science & Research Integrity
- Recognition & Rewards Program
- Impact and Funding

ORFIRA Update Dec 03: Outcome of Scoping Visit (Nov)

Project Duration: Sept 2025 – August 2026

Partner Institution:

Nov 27/28 Scoping Visit: Dr Rita Figueiras Alves dos Santos, AUMC

Summary of requests:

Open Access: how did VU achieve nearly 100% Open Access?

FAIR data management:

- infrastructure for research data management
- Meet coordinator of data steward network

Gamification of engagement with Research community: Open Science games

CoARA: meet contact person for VU's / AUMC's institutional CoARA action plans

Citizen Science Hub: coordination, resources, processes & engagement with the public

NL Recognition & Rewards program:

- Implementation: integration of indicators in annual reviews, promotions etc.
- UCC HR representation?

Next step:

March 02/03 or 09/10, 2026 - UCC Delegation to travel to Amsterdam

ORFIRA Update Jan 14

Introducing an Open Research Framework & Integrating OR indicators into Research Assessment

Amsterdam Visit - to Meet the Experts

Date: Confirmed for March 09/10 (Monday & Tuesday)

Agenda will cover (exact timings TBC):

- Recognition & Rewards Program – Policy, Criteria and Implementation
- Data Steward Network Coordination
- Library: Open Access Implementation
- Open Science:
 - Open Science Training program and resources
 - Embedding Open Science indicators into R&R
 - Citizen Science Hub
- Research Integrity
- AUMC / VU CoARA PoC: CoARA Action Plans

Annex 2 - AUMC Recognition & Rewards Programme

Recognition & Rewards - Amsterdam UMC

Recognition & rewards

VSNU

UMCNL

KNAW

NWO

ZonMw

position paper 2019

Ruimte voor ieders talent

Room for everyone's talent

towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics

> Diversifying and vitalising career paths

We enable more diversity in career paths and profiles for academics.

> Achieving balance between individuals and the collective

We assess academics based on both their individual and their team performance.

> Focusing on quality

In our assessments of academic performance, we increasingly focus on quality, content and creativity.

> Stimulating open science

We encourage academics to share their research outcomes with society.

> Stimulating academic leadership

We stimulate good academic leadership at all levels.

Diversifying and vitalising career paths

1. Enable **diversification and vitalisation of career paths**, thereby promoting excellence in each of the key areas (education, research, impact, leadership and patient care)

Balance between individual & team

2. A better **balance between individual and team performance:**

- Recognition of teamwork and team spirit
- Inspire cooperation between organizations, disciplines and within teams (Team Science)

More focus on quality of work

3. More focus on quality of work

over quantitative results:

- Good scientific research increases scientific knowledge and makes a contribution to solving societal challenges

Stimulating Open Science

4. Open Science becomes the norm and stimulates interaction between scientists and society:

- Stimulating Open Science means recognizing and rewarding other aspects of research (in addition to publications), such as datasets or software, as important research outputs

Stimulating leadership in academia

5. More emphasis on the value of **high-quality leadership in academia** to set the course in research and education, to achieve impact, and to ensure that teams of academics can do their work as well as possible

Project structure R&R

- National coordinating team
 - University's and UMC's (Amsterdam UMC; HR director)
- National Project group
 - Projectleaders uni's en UMCs (Amsterdam UMC; HR project manager)
 - Monthly meetings
- UMCNL working group R&R
 - Every 6 weeks
 - Policy officers research UMC's
- Amsterdam UMC; Committee Talent and Appointments

Participating parties have their own R&R committee that stimulates the intended cultural change at the institutional level by experimenting, inspiring, co-creating, sharing good practices and learning from each other. Good examples can be seen in <https://recognitionrewards.nl/e-magazine/>

Actions R&R 2025 so far

- ✓ • Questionnaire deans (April)
(presentation meeting)
- ✓ • Reaction questions ZonMw (April)
- ✓ • Culture barometer 2026
(preparations start soon)
- ✓ • More visibility on academic career paths intranet
- Criteria for profiles research & education nearly finished
- Valorisation, Clinical and Leadership to be followed shortly
- Open science and team science to be outlined

How to put R&R into practice -career paths

- Career paths with R&R as a guideline put into qualification portfolio's for associate professor, full professor and professor by special appointment (bijzonder hoogleraar)
- Candidates are assessed by way of an 'evidence based CV', by combining narratives providing context to their career choices, with qualitative and quantitative indicators of their academic achievements. They need to excel in at least two of the following domains: research; education; clinical work; valorization and/or academic leadership.

- [Committee for Talent and Appointments | Amsterdam UMC](#) set by the deans of Faculties of Medicine to harmonise talent policy for academic careers in AMC and VUmc and appointment

Annex 4 - RIOS (Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science)

 RIOS webpage

RIOS

We are the Amsterdam Center of Expertise for Research Integrity and Open Science (RIOS):

Connecting initiatives related to research integrity, research ethics, responsible research and innovation, open science, research culture (including recognition and rewards, as well as inclusion, diversity and social safety), and research fairness at the Vrije Universiteit and Amsterdam UMC.

Why RIOS?

Centralised structure

- Overview of RI & OS initiatives
- Ensure initiatives build on each other and do not 'reinvent the wheel'
- Foster mutual learning and capacity

Sustainable Hub

- Connect stakeholders
- Promote interdisciplinary, interfaculty and multi-stakeholder collaboration
- Promote synergies and support

Center of expertise

- Foster learning
- Share knowledge
- Promote active engagement of the community
- Consolidate and expand the leading role in RIOS' themes

Mission

Themes

- Research Integrity
- Research Ethics
- Responsible Research and Innovation
- Open Science
- Research culture (including recognition & rewards, inclusion, diversity and social safety)

Governance – Executive Board

Chair

Professor Mariëtte van
den Hoven

Chair

Professor Jeroen de
Ridder

Coordinator

Dr. Krishma Labib

Project Leader

Dr. Rita F. Alves dos
Santos

Governance – Steering Committee

- Professor René Bekkers – FSW
- Professor Antske Fokkens – FGW
- Professor Paul de Lange – FGB
- Professor Jacco van Ossenbruggen – BETA
- Professor Hans Berends – SBE
- Dr. Sander Bosch – VU Open Science Program
- Professor Cees Kleverlaan – ACTA
- Professor Bart van Klink - RCH

CENTER FOR
RESEARCH INTEGRITY
AND OPEN SCIENCE

RIOS Identity & Dissemination

CENTER FOR
RESEARCH INTEGRITY
AND OPEN SCIENCE

RIOS logo

- RIOS webpage
- RIOS email: info@rios-vu.nl
- RIOS social media channels (LinkedIn and YouTube)
- RIOS Newsletter
- RIOS Flyer & Banner

RIOS Activities - Service & Outreach

Cooperation with
Policy Advisors

Alignment with
Research Strategy

Alignment with VU
OS Program

Internal and external
synergies

Increase visibility

RIOS Activities

Community of Practice *Running*

Research Integrity Training and Supervision
2 meetings

Research Ethics Committees
2 meetings

Amsterdam Metascience group
Prof. dr. René Bekkers & Jack Fitzgerald; monthly
meetings

Open Science for Naturally Occurring Data
Existing community joining RIOS; dr. Bogdana Huma

The poster features a blurred background of a person at a conference with a microphone. It includes the RIOS logo in the top right, the text 'SYMPOSIUM '25' in large blue letters, and event details in a dark blue box at the bottom. A QR code is located in the bottom left corner.

SYMPOSIUM '25

EVENT HIGHLIGHTS:
KEYNOTE SPEAKER
MATCHMAKING WORKSHOP
THE FUTURE OF RESEARCH INTEGRITY & OPEN SCIENCE

FEBRUARY 20
VU AMSTERDAM
For VU and Amsterdam UMC Researchers

FIND MORE INFORMATION AT <https://rios-vu.nl/rios-symposium/>

RIOS Symposium 2025

- 36 participants
- Words of welcome from prof. dr. Jeroen Geurts (VU) & prof. dr. Saskia Peerdeman (AUMC)
- Showcase of ongoing research initiatives on RI & OS;
- Plenary talk by Hans de Jong (Open Science NL)
- Matchmaking event
- RIOS Collaborative Program

RIOS Collaborative Program

- Call for proposals addressing one (or more) of RIOS' pillars;
- Workshop, training, symposium, visiting fellow;
- Clear benefit to the community;
- 8 proposals received;
- 4 supported

RIOS Research

Sustainable RI Training

- Mapping of RI training
- MPowering Responsible Supervision

Fostering a Positive Research Culture

- Interview study
- Survey
- Theatre plays – foster dialogue!

Empowering responsible supervision

A training format
Mariëtte van den
Hoven, Miriam van
Loon, and colleagues

PERSPECTIVE article

Front. Res. Metr. Anal., 04 April 2025

Sec. Research Assessment

Volume 10 - 2025 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2025.1533630>

This article is part of the Research Topic

Evaluating Supervision and Research Leadership in Promoting Responsible Research

[View all articles >](#)

Leading by example: how to empower supervisors as role models

Miriam van Loon

Joeri Tijdink

Natalie Evans

Mariëtte Van Den Hoven*

Department of Ethics, Law and Humanities, Amsterdam University Medical Center, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Supervisors are considered to play a pivotal role in stimulating responsible conduct of research (RCR). Their position as supervisors of PhD candidates offers the opportunity to be good *role models* and show young researchers how to conduct research properly. In this contribution, we delineate what it means to “lead by example.” We inquire how the concept of role modeling is currently applied in the context of supervision in general, and in RCR specifically, and present the perspective of empowerment as a fruitful approach to help determine what role modeling should focus on when aiming to foster a positive research culture.

1 Introduction

Supervisors are considered to play a pivotal role in stimulating responsible conduct of research [RCR; [All European Academies \(ALLEA\), 2023](#); [Lerouge and Hol, 2020](#)]. [Haven et al. \(2022\)](#) described how supervision can both positively and negatively impact the personal and professional development of a PhD candidate. Poor supervision can jeopardize a good working relationship or even stimulate misconduct, while good supervision can integrate young researchers into responsible academic practices and positively boost their academic career and personal development ([Anderson et al., 2007](#); [Pizzolato and Dierickx, 2023b](#)). Note that their position as supervisors makes them *de facto* role models, and in the literature, this role

[Frontiers | Leading by example: how to empower supervisors as role models](#)

Outline

- Context
- Teaching philosophy
- Materials
- Format & content
- Practicalities

Teaching philosophy: Empowerment

Blended approach

Hard skills

- Online modules
- Own pace
- Choice of relevant topics
- Knowledge of rules, guidelines, laws
- Up to date on recent developments

Soft skills

- 2 Onsite 4 hr workshops, obligatory
- Reflection own experiences in supervision and how to improve
- Becoming a responsible supervisor
- Collaboration and communication

Empowering Responsible Supervision will train in...

Hard skills

- Codes of Conduct
- Open science
- Reproducibility and replication
- Research ethics (basics and advanced)
- Data management & privacy
- Publishing

Soft skills

- Responsible Conduct of Research
- Research Culture
- Collaboration
- Supervision styles
- Intercultural differences
- Reflection

RC Interview study

Aims of our study:

- ✓ *To further investigate **how a positive research culture can be fostered in a specific institutional context**, we aim to explore how researchers from different departments and disciplines perceive research culture and how it is related to responsible conduct of research. By using interviews with experts in the field of RCR, we study this context as a case study to inform other settings on how a positive RC could be stimulated.*

Research questions:

- ✓ How do researchers in different faculties define and perceive (aspects of) RC?
- ✓ How could a positive RC be fostered at different levels?

Levels of RC

Some results

- Differences between departments and disciplines in norms and behaviours, and procedures
- Stimulating positive RC:
 - Focus on team work, instead of individual achievements
 - Assess broader aspects of researchers work
 - Stimulate good leadership and supervision

Assessing the perceptions,
experiences and needs of researchers
in Amsterdam for fostering a positive
research culture – survey study

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture

Research Questions:

- ✓ How do researchers perceive and experience their institution's culture regarding responsible conduct of research (RCR) and the recognition and rewards of scientific outputs?
- ✓ What aspects of responsible conduct of research (RCR) and the recognition and rewards of scientific outputs do researchers consider effective or in need of change?
- ✓ Are there differences in how researchers from different ranks and disciplines perceive and experience the research culture at their institution?
- ✓ How do researchers from different backgrounds experience the research culture at their institutions?

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture

Target group

- PhD candidates, junior researchers, Postdoctoral researchers, Assistant, Associate and Full professors, lecturers, heads of department and those with a leadership role (e.g. dean of faculty)

Focus

- Responsible Conduct of Research (e.g. authorship and collaboration, OS, supervision, training)
- Recognition & Rewards (e.g. quality vs quantity, collaboration, society impact)
- Well-being & social safety

Outcomes

- Recommendations to redefine current institutional policies
- Initiatives to raise awareness for a positive research culture
- Joint study with UCC & UJI

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

234 responses (by the 4th November; now 382)

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

Do you identify with a group you feel is underrepresented in academia (e.g. due to ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability or additional needs)?

- ✓ Women
(underrepresentation in higher academic roles)
- ✓ LGBTQ+
- ✓ Race/Religion/Ethnicity
- ✓ International background

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

To what extent do you agree with the following statement...

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

I believe training should be undertaken and made mandatory to...

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

Has the research culture in your institution improved over the past 5 years?

Open science, social safety awareness, infrastructure and personnel (VPs, Ombudsperson), training,...

Budget cuts, competition, publish or perish culture, bureaucracy, unclear criteria for promotion, lack of management skills from heads of department,...

Assessing the perceptions, experiences and needs of researchers in Amsterdam for fostering a positive research culture – preliminary results

RIOS Research

**SCIENCE
HOOPS**
Theatre Plays
on Research Culture

“
An engaging mix of theatre
and dialogue that sparks your
thoughts.
”

MONDAY 24 NOVEMBER 2025
15:00 - 17:00 THEATRE 2

MONDAY 8 DECEMBER 2025
15:00 - 17:00 THEATRE 5

**MENS
IN DE
MAAK** CENTER FOR
RESEARCH INTEGRITY
AND OPEN SCIENCE

RC interview
study

Interactive
scenes

Raise
awareness
and promote
dialogue on +
research
culture

Annex 5 - VU's Open Science Program

OPEN SCIENCE @ VU

INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT

“Based on the conviction that knowledge and science should be accessible and transparent, we stand for the principles of Open Science. VU Amsterdam strives to **publish exclusively in open access**. As research becomes increasingly data-driven, **research protocols, data and analyses have to be made accessible** across the full breadth of the university and in compliance with the FAIR principles: they must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.” - VU Research Vision

“We **share our knowledge and experience** through Open Access, whenever possible. In this way, we contribute to (societal) progress and strengthen our education.” – VU Education Vision

**UNESCO Recommendation
on Open Science**

<https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>
<https://coara.eu/>
https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Key lines of action: Open Access

1. Making all scholarly output **Open Access**;
2. Ensuring that society can reuse all scholarly output;
3. Cost control: **full Open Access** without additional costs;
4. Maintaining high quality and research integrity;
5. Novel ways of **Recognition & Rewards**, away from quantitative measures;
6. Control over ownership, public values, and academic and digital sovereignty;
7. Open services, growing towards less dependency on publishers.

Key lines of action: FAIR Data

1. Build a **professional community of skilled data stewards** that have a wide range of expertise;
2. **Support, guide and incentivise** the generation of sufficiently rich, standardized, open and machineactionable FAIR digital research outputs and associated FAIR metadata to enable optimal (re)use;
3. Enable sustainable interoperable networks of FAIR Data services and research infrastructures at the institutional and domain level and national level;
4. Foster the development of a national trust framework for access to FAIR Data including sensitive and confidential data, in synergy among societal stakeholders.

Key lines of action: Citizen Science

1. **Raise awareness**;
2. Consolidate and further develop best practice;
3. **Build capacity**;
4. Enhance cooperation, synergies, and transdisciplinary collaboration;
5. Develop and invest in supporting infrastructures

VU PROGRAM: TOWARDS OPEN SCIENCE

<https://vu.nl/openscience>
openscience@vu.nl

THE SCOPE

FAIR & RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH

(Open Access)
Publications

(FAIR) Data &
Software

(Open) Research
Process

(Open) Evaluation

(Open) Hardware

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT & IMPACT

Valorisation

Science
Communication

Citizen Science

FAIR & OPEN EDUCATION

(Open) Educational
Resources

(Open) Educational
Formats

(Open) Pedagogy

WHAT DO WE DO?

Academische Loopbaanpaden

	CS*	MP*	NAS	CBR	MCT†	KDHT
Conceptualization	█	█	█	█	█	█
Funding Acquisition	█	█	█	█	█	█
Investigation	█	█	█	█	█	█
Methodology	█	█	█	█	█	█
Resources	█	█	█	█	█	█
Software	█	█	█	█	█	█
Writing	█	█	█	█	█	█

*, † these authors contributed equally

INFRASTRUCTURE @VU

Pure research information system/ publication repository
DMPonline data management planning
ResearchDrive storage
DataverseNL archiving
Yoda implementation of Yoda for storage/archiving
OSF research management, possible integration to other services
RDM administration integration of several overlapping administrative workflows
e-Lab journals research possible solutions
Storage connections Development of links between storage solutions

edusources national platform for open educational resources
CopyRIGHT tool for teachers
Monitoring of OS tracking impact/ monitoring OS practices

2025

NRDS - RDM-administration
NRDS - E-lab journals
NRDS - Develop RDM-infrastructure
OS - Wetenschap in de Wolken - infrastructure for citizen science
OS - Open Research Software

<https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/divisions/university-library/more-about/rdm-tools>
<https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/aurora>
<https://vu.nl/nl/over-de-vu/diensten/universiteitsbibliotheek/meer-over/openleermaterialen>

INFRASTRUCTURE @VU

VU RDM SERVICES 2024

Discover & Initiate

Plan & Design

Collect & Store

Process & Analyse

Document & Preserve

Publish & Share

RDM Support Desk – Service Now rdm@vu.nl

RDM Training (DMP course 2.0, Data- & Software Carpentries, Code Refinery, Data Carpentries, RDM training days, Programming cafe, GHOST coll.)

RDM Information (RDM Libguide, RDS portal) vu.nl/rds RDM Policy 2.0 & Community management & RDS Newsletter

DMP Online & GDPR

Data storage finder

DataverseNL

Data classification tool

Research Drive

Archiving

OSF

Archiving

Scistor 2.0*

Yoda – SRAM connection

eLabJournal

Gitlab – Research Software Management

Qualtrics

Compute facilities*

* Hosted and supported by ITvO

 = sensitive data

 = non sensitive data

 = supports collaboration between Dutch institutes

 = supports external collaboration

 = small data sets <2TB

 = large data sets 2-10TB

SUPPORT & TRAINING

Network RDS

Strengthening support network at the VU within departments

OS/RDM for staff

Embedding of OS/RDM in leadership training

OS/RDM toolkit

Toolkit with OS/RDM resources for BsC/MSC

Carpentries workshops

Growing a Carpentries community

Research Software

Pilot SMP, development of support & information

Management

RDM Handbook

Collaborative handbook on OS/RDM

OER Support

Creation of an OER Support Desk

Taxila

2025

NRDS/OS - Discipline-specific training/ guidelines for VU researchers

OS - Support for knowledge platform openresearch.Amsterdam

NRDS/OS - national collaboration on training

<https://rdm.vu.nl/>
rdm@vu.nl

 openresearch.amsterdam

<https://vu-libcal.com/calendar/universitylibrary?cid=7052&t=g&d=0000-00-00&cal=7052&inc=0>
<https://openresearch.amsterdam/>
<https://taxila.nl/>

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Community support

GHOST collective

Engagement campaign

ORCID campaign

Events and symposia

Open Science games

Awareness and engagement campaign for OS/RDM/OER

Games of
Horror for
Open
Science
Training

VU
VRIJE
UNIVERSITEIT
AMSTERDAM

2025

NRDS/OS - RDM/OS Community management

OS – Ambassadors with faculties/departments

OS – Fund for community events

OS – VU Open Science award

OS - Support OSCA/ SIOS (e.g. with OSCAwards)

<https://osc-international.com/osc-amsterdam/>
<https://studentinitiativeopenscience.wordpress.com/>
<https://ghostcollective.github.io/>

Games of Horror for Open Science Training

28 October 2025 12:00 - 13:00

Add to Calendar

Sign up

Hey data enthusiast, Does Open Science confound you enough to ask the spirits for help? Join us for the launch of our new GHOST game Open Séance - in which you team up with a medium to determine the perfect open science for your research.

The [GHOST Collective](#) (Games of Horror for Open Science Training) made hit card games such as Open Science against Humanity, Open Loves Science and Open Science Alliance. During this session we'll focus on playing the newest game, but there will be possibilities to try the wide arrangement of other games.

12:00 - Welcome + Lunch

12:10 - Introduction to GHOST collective

12:20 - Open Séance playtesting

Data horror week

2020

2021

2022

2023

Open Science against Humanity

Yo, — is open
science, right?

Paying 1800 euro
to put a PDF
online

1

**Work load piling
up and sanity
breaking down**

2

**Confidently
ignoring all
inquiries of groups
trying to replicate
my research**

3

**Financing the
fourth boat of
Elsevier's CEO**

**There is no
competition in
science, there
is just _____**

4

**Budget cuts until
your research
team exists of
you and your
mom (who
volunteered)**

2024

OPEN SCIENCE

Open science

The Library
“Libraries as Open
Innovators and
Leaders”

2025 Open Science Alliance

RECOGNITION & REWARDS

Academische Loopbaanpaden

Road show
Art of Engagement Leadership/
Tenure-track policy
Commitment
Registration workflows

Discussions within faculties/ services
team membership workshop
Align tenure-track policy with R&R
To R&R/ DORA/ Open Science
Which information do we want to register in
our Current Research Information System (CRIS)?
Make use of CRedit roles in publications
and assessment

Pilot CRedit

	CS*	MP*	NAS	CBR	MCT†	KDHT
Conceptualization						
Funding Acquisition						
Investigation						
Methodology						
Resources						
Software						
Writing						

*, † these authors
contributed equally

2025

Open Science within yearly appraisal meetings/ PhD policy
Optimised registration of Open Science of research output
Aurora Open Science Monitor

<https://credit.niso.org/>
https://assets.vu.nl/d8b6f1f5-816c-005b-1dc1-e363dd7ce9a5/de3480c3-3962-4a3e-a934-b61fe6deb90e/Academic%20Careerpath%202023%20VU_EN.pdf

Dr Sander Bosch – s.e.bosch@vu.nl
Tycho Hofstra – t.m.hofstra@vu.nl

Annex 3 - VU Recognition & Rewards Programme

Guide to academic career paths

For academics with an appointment as assistant professor, associate professor or full professor, and their managers

Academic career paths in brief

Whom does it concern?

All academics with an appointment as assistant professor, associate professor or full professor.

What is the idea?

With your manager, agree on a focus in one of the core domains: education, research or impact. Whatever your focus may be, combining education and research continues to be the core of any academic career. This combination is and will remain fundamental.

How do you make agreements on this?

In the annual consultation with your manager, based on what suits you best *and* makes an optimal contribution to the objectives of the collective: your team, department or faculty.

Why are we doing this?

It is neither realistic nor necessary for every academic to excel in all core domains. Many academics are currently experiencing too much emphasis on research performance, which puts pressure on ambitions in education, impact and leadership.

When will this take effect?

In 2025. The annual consultation always takes place between 1 February and 31 December.

More information about this can be found in this [guide](#)

Equal appreciation

At VU Amsterdam, we believe it is important that our academic staff can develop in a direction that suits them and that together they can excel and contribute to the greater whole.

This is why VU is working on appreciating all academic aspects and domains equally, with more attention for qualitative aspects and performance in the areas of education, social impact and leadership, and less emphasis on quantitative indicators.

Collaboration and complementarity

Instead of striving for excellence in all domains, you mainly focus on what suits you best and makes an optimal contribution to the objectives of the collective (your faculty or department).

A successful academic environment consists of academics with different talents, areas of expertise and interests.

If each team member develops specific expertise and engages in collaboration, the collective becomes better than any individual academic can be on their own.

‘It takes diversity and the interplay of talents and skills to make for a good team’

Recognition & Rewards: what will change?

From	To
Main focus on research results	All academic domains are appreciated equally Alongside teaching and research, this also means appreciating educational innovations and impact
Little regard for the assurance of academic integrity and social safety	Aspects that assure academic integrity and social safety are conditional to performance assessments and promotion. Examples include leadership, teamwork and open science
Too much emphasis on quantitative research and other indicators (H-index, Impact Factor, funding acquisition) in performance assessments and promotion	Balance between qualitative and quantitative assessment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no quantitative measures without a qualitative explanation • and 360 degree feedback
Academics 'must' excel at everything	Academics must meet the basic requirements for education and research, and the impact thereof, and excel – by choice and agreement – in one of the domains of teaching, research or impact
Focus mainly on excelling within one discipline	More room for and recognition of the development of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary skills
Individual performance first	The contribution to the team and academic community is more important, for example in the form of organisational and/or institutional responsibilities. The more senior the academic, the more important it becomes to coach colleagues in the role of mentor
Career path strongly focused on vertical promotion	The career path is more diversified, with both horizontal and vertical development and opportunities for further growth
'Career guidance' based on performance agreements	Career guidance is focused on supporting professional and personal development, taking into account life course influences

What concrete changes will be made to academic career paths?

As of 2025, all academics with an appointment as assistant professor, associate professor or full professor will make agreements with their manager on a focus in one of the core domains: education, research or impact.

This way, you determine the emphasis within your career, by agreement and within the scope available. You also agree on the period during which this applies. Switching focus domains is possible (especially at the start of your career). You always continue to work and develop in the dual domains of education and research, as this combination is and will remain fundamental.

In your annual consultation, you agree how you can continue to develop in this core domain. Every year, you discuss how your development in this domain is going.

Career paths and development scope

Horizontal steps offer opportunities for growth by shifting the focus to another domain, a supporting or management position or outside the academic context. In this case, the organisational responsibility stays the same.

A **vertical** career step means more responsibility within the organisational unit, university, academic discipline or in society.

Recognition & Rewards Academic career paths and development paths

Diversification of career paths

From quantity to quality

Open science

Leadership

Balance between the individual and the collective

Educational Development Path

As of 2025, this is how it will work

As an academic with an assistant professor/ associate professor/full professor profile:

- You consult the departmental or faculty strategy and faculty criteria for the focus domains
- You reflect on your own career path (The [academic path reflection questions](#) will be helpful in this regard)
- You discuss this path and your development need with your direct manager
- You make agreements with your manager on a focus on one of the core domains

As a manager:

- You share the departmental or faculty strategy
- You explore the individual development needs of your academic staff
- You align all of the team members' wishes and opportunities with each other and the departmental plan
- You give feedback on everyone's development

Together, you make development agreements
(in the annual consultation)

Step by step

Annual consultation

The [annual consultation](#) is a moment to look back and ahead and make agreements about the things you do and how you do them. The structure of the consultation is flexible, so you can shape it together based on joint responsibility. This enables you to discuss broader topics, such as collaboration and career planning. As of 2025, assistant professors, associate professors and full professors will additionally discuss their focus on a core domain.

As a good consultation starts with good preparation, [here](#) you will find an explanation of who does what, which tools are available and how you register the consultation in the annual consultation form.

Career paths for individual academics

The below questions will give you a general idea of how you can discuss career opportunities

1. Is the scientist an assistant professor/ associate professor/full professor?	no → yes →	An academic career path with an emphasis on a focus domain is not relevant (yet). The academic can explore how their development is going in the context of the academic career paths.
2. Does the academic have the capacity for self reflection and are they developing in terms of: • the three aspects of leadership, • management (if applicable), • and training & development in accordance with the position?	no → yes →	A next career step is not possible yet. Make agreements on the required development steps with regard to one or several of these topics A next career step is possible: horizontal or vertical.
3. Does the academic meet the position's basic requirements when it comes to the core domains (as they apply at the faculty)?	no → yes →	Choosing an emphasis in one of the domains is not yet relevant and the focus is on meeting the basic requirements or progressing to another position (within or outside VU Amsterdam). The academic can explore their preferences and wishes with regard to a next step. In an annual consultation with the manager, preferences and scope within the faculty are discussed.
4. Does the academic see a match between their wish and the scope for focus domains with their faculty/department?	no → yes →	Explore alternatives and make agreements on how to continue. Discuss with your manager and make joint career agreements within the scope available.

Tools for academics

- [Academic career paths](#)
- [Reflection questions](#)
- [Annual consultations](#)

Strategic Personnel Plan (SPP) manager

The below steps will give you an insight into your Strategic Personnel Plan (SPP)

1. Needed in the future

Ambition:

- Where do we want to go with the faculty/ department and why?
- What expertise does this require in the short and long term?

Can you give a convincing answer to these questions?

no →

yes →

Ensure it is clear what is demanded from your department/faculty. Discuss this with your manager or ask fellow managers for help.

[Go to point 2](#)

2. Already present (staff review)

Where are we:

- What expertise is already present (in terms of positions, expertise in core domains, leadership, management skills, etc.)?
- What are the academic team's wishes and opportunities?

Can you give a convincing answer to these questions?

no →

yes →

Check with other managers within or outside your department how they go about this. Ask for help from the HR Advisor and/or your manager.

[Go to point 3](#)

3. Match between present and future

Bridge/differences:

- Where does it and where does it not yet match?
- Are you able to make the match (short and long term plan) and explain it to your team?

Can you give a convincing answer to these questions?

no →

yes →

Make sure you gather knowledge on how to go about this. For example, plan a meeting with your own manager and/or HR.

[Initiate actions that help maintain success factors and bridge problematic differences.](#)

Questions?

Annex 6 – Reserch Integrity at VU

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

Dr. Rita F. Alves dos Santos

Coordinator of the Netherlands Research Integrity Network ([NRIN](#))
Project Leader of the Center of expertise for Research Integrity and Open Science
([RIOS](#))

Netherlands CoC for Research Integrity

- ✓ Revised version in 2026
- ✓ Endorsed by:
 - 📖 Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)
 - 📖 Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU)
 - 📖 Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)
 - 📖 Associated Applied Research Institutes (TO2 federation)
 - 📖 Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences
 - 📖 Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU)

Netherlands CoC for Research Integrity

- ✓ The standards for good research practices set out what researchers must take into consideration in their work, individually and as a team.
- ✓ Mostly presented for each individual phase of the research process:
 - Design
 - Conduct
 - Reporting
 - Assessment & peer review
 - Communication

Netherlands CoC for Research Integrity

- ✓ The Code also sets the duties of care (mandates) that institutions should apply to foster research integrity:
 - RI training (mandatory for PhD candidates)
 - Resources and institutional policies
 - Fair evaluation of cases of misconduct (RI Committees)
 - Personnel (Confidential Advisors, Policy Advisors / Research Integrity Coordinators)
 - Space for dialogue and mutual learning (NRIN platform)

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

Research Integrity

Scientific research has to be reliable and honest. VU creates a working environment in which the standards for good research practices are adhered to, informed by the normative framework in the **Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018**. How? This is shown below.

Support	Organize	Communicate
<p>Research environment RI-coordinators promote awareness. There are several options for help, support and advice. Balancing recognition and rewards encourages RI, e.g. through self-reflection.</p>	<p>Research ethics Ethical review is mandatory in medical scientific research involving human participants (WMO). For non-WMO there are faculty ethical review committees per research area.</p>	<p>Research collaboration Know the guidelines for contractual partnerships. Involve IXA-GO for support on externally funded research collaborations, and valorization and impact.</p>
<p>Supervision and mentoring PhD Candidate Advisors support PhD students. Supervisors receive training in supervision. The doctorate regulations govern matters concerning thesis such as a plagiarism check.</p>	<p>RI-issues and complaints procedure The confidential RI-counsellor advises and assists in RI-issues. The Academic Integrity Committee advises on the merits of complaints in line with the Academic integrity complaints procedure.</p>	<p>Declaration of interests Ancillary activities are paid or unpaid tasks carried out for third parties. These require prior consent from your supervisor.</p>
<p>Integrity training All PhD students attend a mandatory RI-course. Each faculty has a confidential RI-counsellor who is centrally supported through intervention and training.</p>	<p>Data Management Research Data Management enables secure sharing and re-use of research data. Data stewards and privacy champions offer support. The LibGuide toolbox provides practical info and guidelines.</p>	<p>Publication and communication Publish according to authorship guidelines. Media training supports careful press and science communication.</p>

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

Overseen by graduate schools in each faculty!

Mandatory RI training for PhD candidates

- Discipline specific training on topics such as authorship, data management, open science, supervision, ethics, etc.

Mandatory training for early career supervisors

- Assistant professors who have just started to supervise (0-5 years)
- Training provided at the central level

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

PhD Peer Intervention

- Discuss challenges during the PhD trajectory
- Career outlook, supervision, budget, etc.

Writing Lab

- Support in improving academic writing skills
- PhD thesis writing tips
- Specially designed for international students

UTK/BKO for PhDs

- For PhD students who want to develop their teaching skills
- Certified training

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

Empowering Responsible
Supervision
(AUMC - also planned to
be available for VU
employees)

Research Integrity – policies, practices and approaches

Annex 7 – Agenda for Visit of UCC delegation to AUMC on March 09/10 2026

CoARA ORFIRA Amsterdam Meeting Agenda

Day 1 – 9th March 2026

Location- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Forum 7

Time	
09:30 – 10:00	Welcome Rita F. Alves dos Santos
10:00 – 11:00	Inspired Supervision and other available trainings from the Center for Teaching and Learning (CTL) Allard Gerritsen, Coordinator of CTL trainings
11:00 – 12:00	VU Amsterdam CoARA action dr. Richard de Waard, VU CoARA representative
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch
13:00 – 14:00	Embedding Open Science into the researchers' assessment policies – insights from the Open Science NL Publication Steward project Marián Crespo López, Researcher
14:00 - 14:45	Overview of the day and project progress Rita F. Alves dos Santos
14:45 – 15:45	Amsterdam UMC Recognition & Rewards policies – criteria and indicators on academic career paths dr. Marjon van Wijnbergen, Policy Advisor for AUMC R&R
19:00 – 22:00	Dinner

Day 2 – 10th March 2026

Location- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – Forum 7

Time	
09:30 – 10:00	Welcome Rita F. Alves dos Santos
10:00 – 11:00	Network of Data Stewards dr. Marcel Raas, Coordinator of Network of Data Stewards
11:00 – 12:00	Open Access at VU Amsterdam Dr. Anne van den Maagdenbergen, Open Access Librarian
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch
13:00 – 14:00	Research Integrity policies and procedures Dorien Sorel, VU RI Policy Advisor
14:00 – 16:00	VU Open Science Program & training, Citizen Science initiatives and Open Science indicators and criteria into R&R policies dr. Sander Bosch, VU Chief Open Science

Annex 8

Work plan, Resources, and outputs/deliverables

Phase 1 (month 1-3):

- project kick-off with representation from Amsterdam and UCC OVPRI, ULT (university leadership team), HR, library and 4x colleges
- Nominate 'Open Research Champions' in all key areas in UCC
- Plan and arrange a partner visit itinerary for phase 2
- Gap analysis: ambitions vs. current use of Open Research practices, barriers

Deliverables: Gap analysis, Full itinerary for phase 2

Phase 2 (month 4): Learning visit of UCC project team and college representatives to Amsterdam to understand Amsterdam UMC's Open Science implementation in each faculty:

- Amsterdam UMC Open Science framework, scope, definitions and priorities
- Amsterdam UMC Open Science community, ambassadors / champions network,
- training and supports available, technical infrastructure, indicators and their integration into research assessment

Deliverable: Partner visit report

Phase 3 (Month 5 – 6):

- Draft an implementation proposal (aligned with creation of CoARA action plan) and identify priority items for realistic implementation within the project timeline
- All stakeholders co-develop UCC's Open Research framework and ambition: definitions, scope, champions / ambassadors, training resources, infrastructure, indicators & assessment criteria in line with CoARA principles
- Map how Open Research framework translate into each college/unit
- Cascade the framework into colleges through champions/ambassadors and
 - develop indicators relevant to disciplines
 - identify integration routes into assessment and recognition schemes
- Reach consensus & secure senior leadership support for Implementation plan
- **Deliverables: OR Framework (priority + long list), Priority item Implementation plan**